

RE-DISCOVERING THE AFRICAN PHILOSOPHY OF THE ARCHITECTURE THROUGH THE OTHER/OTHER'S LENS. EUROPEAN-BASED CONSIDERATIONS.

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The Western definitions of the "smart cities" are concentrated around three main elements. First approach describes the "smart city" as the organized body, using the new technologies in the manner to increase the efficiency of the infrastructure and communication interconnectivity (Azkuna, 2012). Another approach emphasizes the role of the sensors, mobile devices, to create digital dimension of the city (Schaffers, 2012). Yet another approach presents the city as the area consisting of populations implementing activities and effectively acting institutions in terms of knowledge creation, developed broadband infrastructure and on-line tools for knowledge management and solving problems that arise for the first time, as the key to the assessment of the intelligence (Komninos, 2008). The main thesis of the paper is that the process of incorporation of the Western-based "smart cities" concepts into the developing African cities can be dangerous for their identities, if not preceded by an epistemological reflection upon African cultures. From the perspective of a European philosopher and architect, the African cultural memory, emphasizing the interconnectivity of beings and environments, is the crucial element of the African systems of perception. It is applied and visible in the contemporary architecture in the landscape, but its lack describes the architecture of the cities. The adaptation of the OTHER (technologically grounded) concept into the African context demands primarily exploring HERE the original philosophy of architecture (theoretical, practical). This philosophy would act as a medium connecting the contemporaneity with cultural resources and the new technologies with existing urban and architectural tissues. The thesis and some re-discovered through the OTHER/OTHER'S lens propositions for African architectural philosophy will be illustrated by examples of the architecture of Namibia, Burkina Faso and South Africa.

Historical legacy

While studying scientific papers and documents concerning Africa one gradually becomes surprised that, despite quite long lasting relations between African and Western cultures (dating from the Renaissance period), an African continent still appears to Europeans as a mysterious land (Sieber and Walker, 1987). On the one hand it fascinates, on the other it terrifies. A closer look at the reasons for such an ambiguous attitude reveals that in spite of a great amount of the anthropological researches, the cultural background of the continent is still unrecognized for Europeans (because of that, Europeans locate their ‘African considerations’ in a colonial, romanticized discourse, or in the apartheid-routed one). Explaining the background of the contemporary situation of already independent Africa the researchers point at the reasons for this situation. The first and most crucial one arose during the period of colonialism, when the main source of understanding of African reality, an orality (linked to race, sex, religion and phobias) was assigned the negative value and became opposed to the positively evaluating Western literacy. Enforced by the positive law and the concept of primitiveness treating the Blackness as a disability, members of the Western civilization smashed the native African religions and destroyed indigenous artistic expression connected to orality (Cartwright, 1851; Cesaire, 1957; Cook and Lindau, 2000; Eze, 1997; Mapoure, 2011; Mucina, 2013; Sieber and Walker, 1987). Among the “colonial legacy” of the technological nature (intended as a replacement of indigenous heritage) one can find the implementation of Western concepts of progress and the development based on engineering, prescribing the colonial design and spatial ordering as mechanisms of control over African family life, working conditions and the cultural memory (Demissie, 2004; Kamete, 2013; Müller-Friedmann, 2008). Spatial planning was realized through the introduction of statistics based concepts of standards of living, treating it as a method of civilizing Natives, also through the reconstruction of the local space in the form of European architecture and aesthetics, as far as incorporating suburban-style architecture from the British planning tradition, and implanting colonial culture and institutions (Asomani-Boateng, 2011; Demissie, 2004; Morange and al., 2012; Mucina, 2013; Müller-Friedmann, 2006, 2008; Peters, 2004; Steinmetz and Hell, 2006).

The culminating moment of the development of the colonial period in architecture is identified with the beginning of modern movement in South Africa. Theoretical assumptions of the modern movement became the main ideology of the authorities, and in a form of the spatial solutions underlay the process of the restructuring and civilizing black and coloured members of the society (Kamete, 2013; Popke and Ballard, 2004). Orderly pleasing cities, amenable to intervention through design, management and engineering was the main goal of it (Bauman, 1993). From the point of view of abovementioned dialectics of the formal order and beauty, “disorder” and spatial “unruliness” connected to the informal settlements, although treated as inevitable in the restructuring process, was assigned for eradication. Through the law and administrative regulations during the apartheid period informality was equated with illegality and opposed to formality – both: spatial and legal (Abdoul, 2005, ILO 1972; Tokman 2001; Castells and Portes 1989). That allowed the authorities to develop certain modes of dealing with urban informality, described as “de-informalization” relocation/delocation, eradication and “repressive tolerance” (Marcuse, 1969; Butcher, 1986; Robins, 2002; Rupiya, 2005; Maponga, 2006; Kamete, 2002a, 2002b, 2013; Mooya and

Cloete, 2007; Simposya, 2010; Tipple, 2000). It revealed that city landscapes were still based on the racial distinctions: a modernist part assigned for the white residents, the townships - for the black and coloured urbanites. A glorification of the colonial past and leftovers of the romanticized Africanness still took place in architectural education (Marschall, 2001).

During the apartheid period and after, two further ideological concepts of so called “African philosophy of the architecture” arose. According to the first of them called ‘Africanness’, the original design is supposed to be

“the more or less superficial coding of a building with highly visibly and recognizable elements that signify to the users or viewers a sense of Africa, or that constitute an ‘African character’ in the eyes of predominantly non-African viewers” (Marschall, 2001, p. 140).

It was also suggested that

“Africanness must be contrasted with Afrocentrism, which can be defined as an attempt to replace Europe (or the West) with Africa as the general reference point for the (re)production of all knowledge [Olaniyan, 1995, 93]. Afrocentrism is related to movements such as PanAfricanism, Negritude and Black Consciousness, all of which are different, complex and historically conditioned concepts in their own right, but their common denominator is the intention to reform the consciousness of black Africans in relation to whites, the cultural and ideological struggle against colonization, and the emphasis on self-determination and self-construction. Afrocentrism is a profound and all encompassing (i.e. social, political, cultural) movement [Olanyian, 1995, 97], which is first and foremost meaningful to black Africans (although theoretically addressed at anyone). Africanness ...is predominantly addressed to whites; it does not aim at a profound reshaping of consciousness, or of architectural design for that matter, but refers to the (often exoticised) ‘African’ coding of buildings that are designed by white architects for a predominantly white audience” (Marschall, 2001, p. 140).

Describing the situation of the contemporary designing at the continent, Sabine Marschall stresses that:

“The majority of architects in South Africa reject any encoding of a building with culturally specific references and follow architectural ‘styles’ that are clearly linked to broader international trends, such as neo-modernism. A few, however, are trying by all means to ‘Africanise’ their architectural designs. This trend enjoys the greatest popularity in the commercial field and establishments addressed at a tourist audience, but is also found in private residential architecture and even in civic architecture with considerable public and symbolic status” (Marschall, 2001, p. 140). Marschall remains also that:

“The Eurocentric bias of architecture in South Africa—its educational foundations, its underlying theories and practices—have become a matter of debate and (sometimes) criticism” (Marschall, 2001).

Towards the original philosophy of design of the architecture

One of the thesis of this paper is that Africa needs its own philosophy of architecture rooted in the indigenous knowledge which, in fact, has the cultural origin. Thus, the most appropriate scientific discipline which may serve as the source of the methodology for the further grounds for the architectural design seems to be a sensorial anthropology. Since the methodology of Western sciences/philosophies are based on distinguishing and individuating the senses according to a proximal stimulus, representation, phenomenal character and a sense organ - a chosen principle for the individuation of the senses results in stressing the different ranges of the environmental properties (Macpherson, 2011; Nudds, 2004, p. 45). But while European sciences/philosophies consider those properties in connection to distinguished and individuating senses, in African reality this methodology seems to be unproper. The prove for such assumption one can find already at the language level – some of African languages do not even have the terms and notions describing five separate, physically/biologically individuated senses (Geurts, 2003).

The beginning of every kind of Western philosophy/epistemology is located in everyday sensory experiences. The cultural research made so far by the sensory anthropologists have proved that human sensory experience is an effect of the somatic work of human being upon the cultural and existential contents, in the other words - the linguistic as well as alinguistic experiences of individuals, which stay in the various relations (creative, maintaining, interrupting, communicative) with interpersonal or cultural notions of moral, aesthetic, or logical desirability (Hewy and Classen, 1991; Classen, 1998, 2005; Howes, 1991, 2003, 2005; Stoller, 1989, Seremetakis, 1994, Macpherson, 2011, Van Ende, 2009; Vanini, Waskull, Gotschalk, 2012). Those relations reveal that somatic rules which organize sensorial impressions are underlaid by numerous circumstances of symbolic, corporeal, cultural, physical, ritualized and improvised nature (Huxley, 1942; Vanini, Waskull, Gotschalk, 2012). The recognition of the particular sets (modes) of the relations among those circumstances, exposed in the observed shape, informs us what sense is important for practical purposes and which one is important for the culturally sensory coding (Vanini, Waskull, Gotschalk, 2012; Howes, 2003; Roadway, 1994; Rivelin and Gravell, 1984).

The relevance of the given sensory expression (code) of the sensory experience can be determined by relating it to the total sensory dynamics of the culture. Since the senses mediate between the mind and body, they mediate between meaning and materiality, and further – between meaning, object and action - all changing through passing time. The sensory experiences in African reality are produced, enacted and perceived as intertwined with emotion, meaning and memory. What emerges between the sensory modes and the cultural codes is the actual sensory perception. It becomes the main element of African philosophies/epistemologies, among them - especially present in the Ubuntu theory.

Ubuntu philosophy as the grounds for the philosophy of the architectural designing

From the perspective of the European philosopher and architect it is claimed that contemporary philosophy of the African architecture which could constitute the theoretical grounds for the further/future design, should be rooted in the Ubuntu theory. For that purpose the most important from the design point of view is the Ubuntu epistemology.

According to Devi D. Mucina the beginning point of it is located in the concept of the Africana phenomenological position: I am because you are, which means the self-reflective descriptions of the constituting activities of the consciousness of **Africana** people (Henry, 2006, p. 1, Mucina, 2013, p. 30). Mucina explains that the self-reflection and its active meaning making occur in a multidimensional, relational world: the social meaning of our world is made through the older meaning of it, created before by the self-reflection and meaning making of our ancestors.

Starting from the self-reflection and old meanings created by ancestors, the construction of the new categories and rules for architectural philosophy of design demands saving meanings of the spatial and architectural categories and elements of so far existing environment. The next step is to recognize the Ubuntu position (understood as an 'inward-looking process' of understanding one's actual relations inside multi-dimensional reality) in the sensory experiences. The change created in comparison to the passing phenomena (presence of which is accessible through the form of the sensory codes) has to be understood in relationship to space, giving in this way the rise to the concept of its occupation.

As doings create changes, architectural designing actions should be constantly preceded by the contested interpretation of the new social and spatial concepts being constituted during the changing phenomena. To achieve this, the main theoretical task for new architectural philosophy is to interpret relational bounds revealing how the change, according to the Ubuntu epistemology, the constant fact, impacts everything (Mucina, 2013). To understand the interweaving binds of time, space and action it is necessary to investigate the relation of the past and the present meanings, coding the newly emerging concept into the experience; experience is conceived of as the embodiment meaning of rules concerning how to design, occupy and manage the space.

Ubuntu Philosophy and the Contemporary Design: Case Studies.

From the point of view of the architectural and urban development of the African cities it is important to recognize whether recently realized (after the restoration of the independence/sovereignty) particular buildings are created in accordance with the cultural dynamics of sensory perception (essential for the Ubuntu epistemology). After having analyzed different contemporary buildings realized in Southern Africa, we present below three examples which reveal some elements of emergent architectural discourse in terms of the Ubuntu philosophy.

Diébégo Francis Kéré, Primary School, Gando, Burkina Faso

Figure 1. Primary School, Gando, Burkina Faso (Kéré, 2004).

The main intention of Diébégo Francis Kéré was to build a permanent building that will serve the people from Gando village (which Kéré comes from) for many years. The architect decided to realize a school, perceiving the construction of it as increasing of an opportunity for education for his countrymen. It was also expected that the building of the school would stop the migration of people from the countryside to the city, as well as give the local community (involved in a building process) an opportunity to gain the knowledge of the technologies and apply them to improve traditional building techniques, as well as to reinforce local building materials. Kéré envisaged that the skills learned by the members of the community in this way would be applied to further initiatives in the village for its own purposes, as well as let one use competences to get a job outside the village. He introduced the technologies reinforcing local techniques and materials in terms of their durability. Kéré taught how to effectively strengthen the dried blocks of clay, melted and eroded under the influence of rainfalls and strong winds, and how to produce more permanent compressed earth blocks. The solution was to stabilize those block with 8% cement. For that purpose he imported a machine from Belgium. Because of the costly protection of local wood against termites, the wood was replaced with steel. Additionally, the villagers learned how to weld the steel trass structure of the roof. The other building solutions were being developed on site: a double open-work roof structure resembling a tree, a brick ceiling with a slit allowing ventilation and top-lighting, extended eaves (roof) to protect the walls against the sun, the building orientation reducing the direct sunlight exposure (the shortest side exposed to the sun).

Peter Rich, Alexandra Interpretation Center, Johannesburg, South Africa

Figure 2. Alexandra Interpretation Centre, Johannesburg, South Africa (Hall, 2011).

The building of the Alexandra Interpretation Centre was assigned as an envisaged and secured place for common meetings of the Black and coloured citizens of the Alexandria borough in Johannesburg – the place where divided so far communities of the township could gather, unite and experience different events together. The rules according to which design was conceptualized were the effect of Rich's reinterpretation of the architecture of Southern Ndebela (Mapogga) and Bantwane. Among the main elements Van Wyk specifies the open-ended formal layout, often asymmetrically corrected; expressing the social order (changing over the time) the planning of the structure, with accordance to the demands of the occupants; enclosures formed by buildings losing fitting outdoor rooms and courtyards; the internal and external spaces acting as one; the transition from public to private space clearly defined; entrance thresholds extended in many ways; the structure of the building revealing the way of building and the materials (Van Wyk, 2002, p. 221) .

Peter Rich's architectural design process was preceded by a series of design sketches and social surveys (Hall, 2011). Not being Black and not living in the district of Alexandra, Rich - unlike Kéré - studied the life styles and family life organisation of people in the place. He visited homes, analysed the features, materials and other elements in terms of spatial organization, size and scale (Stanescu, 2010). The intention of such research was to get to the source of the value system of the users and recognize what precisely united them. As a result, he proposed a design whose construction and structure are opened for the future happenings and changes. It proved to be solution which was valid even after a three years break in the construction building process. The open-ended design referred to its informal surroundings, gave the building credibility to the authenticity, reinforced by the introduction of the vivid, coloured polycarbonate window panels. At the same time he assumed to apply technologies which were easy and friendly to use. The fact, that the building was erected over the road was also important as it helped to legitimise the existing, informal meeting place as the official area, accepted by the communities as their own.

Carin Smuts (CS Studio Architects), Guga S'thebe Arts & Cultural Centre, Cape Town, South Africa

Figure 3. Guga S'Thebe Arts & Cultural Centre, Cape Town, South Africa (Phaidon Ed., 2005).

In the case of Guga S'Thebe Arts & Cultural Centre in the Langa Township, the principle of a village spatial organization was implemented into the post-apartheid reality. The design carrying the shadow over the common areas, creates also the support for the glass roof that opens the space up to the sky. The spatial organization opened inwards makes people working there feeling that they belong to the community similarly to the examples of indigenous Africa urban forms and architecture (Asomani-Boateng, 2011). In this case the important element was the realization of the traditional sensory cultural coding in the shape of the artistic tile mosaic. The brightly coloured building is dedicated to the empowerment of the people of Langa and improvement of the communication and cooperation between ethnical groups, also in the area of economics (Phaidon Ed., 2005). The building is approachable from different sides. Thus, the post-apartheid grid of streets is broken.

Case Studies Interpretation

Francis D. Kéré took advantage of the traditional knowledge generated by the cultural practices to introduce the innovative techniques which were adapted to local conditions and accepted by the local community. That let for maintaining its identity and integrity. It would not have been possible without the acceptance and previous interpretation/adaptation of the sensory experience of the members of the community revealing the cultural memory. Mutual communication mediated by it (meaning making activity) played an important role during the construction process (Kéré, 2004). That did not only allow for the cultivation of material and cognitive heritage but also produced new circumstances for the change, revealing the dynamics of the culture.

The Alexandra Interpretation Center is an example of the interpretation and adaptation of the dynamics of the life experience, saving opened for the change the external and internal spaces, redefining the formal layout in accordance to the circumstances of the urban landscape but leaving aside the social order. That helped in creating the spaces for maintaining the value system shared by the citizens. It means the presence of both: the

Ubuntu foundations in the forms of cultural dynamics of the sensory perception and phenomenological position, in that way preparing the grounds for the further realization of the ethics of reconciliation.

Similarly to the previous examples Guga S'Thebe Arts & Cultural Centre in the Langa Township is opened to the informal structures taking place inside. Here the model of community rooted in indigenous African cultures serves as the tool for bringing people together, allowing for cooperation and sharing the histories, evoking that way interwoven in the Ubuntu Philosophy the multidimensional African reality. Thus, designs that are supposed to realize sensory perception in accordance with the sensory dynamics of the culture and connection to the Ubuntu epistemology should be opened for interconnectivity of all kind of organization of the spaces defined through the interweaving of the structural elements of the building. Design should allow for maintaining the relationships between particular elements of the structure within wholeness of particular multidimensional environment, which – in fact – usually defines the design (Guga S'Thebe Arts & Cultural Centre, Alexandra Interpretation Centre, both in South Africa, Single Quarters Market (Fig.4) in Namibia, Primary School Gando in Burkina Faso). Thanks to that the colonial and postcolonial realizations are being included into the contemporary thinking of designing the cities, as it formes the heritage of the city tissue. Allowance for a long time access, enabling the organization of events and creating conditions for the community to be together, are, in practice, achieved by the structures with many entrances – external (to the street) and internal (connecting intertwined internal spaces).

Figure 4: Single Quarters Market, Marais, Pretorious&Wenhold Architects, Windhoek, Namibia (Rynkowska-Sachse and Sachse, 2013).

The abovementioned requirements are not meet in the majority of commercial buildings completed in African cities, created in order to satisfy the needs of tourists and the rich members of African societies - both the white and the black (Umenne, Rynkowska-Sachse, 2013). Considering the relations between the elements of a larger environment, some of those commercial buildings are open both to the landscape and people (The Village incorporates the landscape of the hill, is open to the rich, Ernst & Young Headoffice constitutes the landscape as the part of the building, both in Windhoek, Namibia).

Figure 5: The Village, Barnard Mutua Architects, Windhoek, Namibia
(Rynkowska-Sachse, 2013)

Figure 6: Ernst & Young Headoffice, Wasserfall Muntig Architects Windhoek, Namibia
(Sachse, 2013)

Unfortunately, recently completed buildings outside the city (Mowani Mountain Camp (Fig.7), like Kipve Camp and Little Kulala in Namibia, although open to the surrounding, still fulfill the romanticized requirements of the visitors as to, among the others, the inspiration of the shapes of nature and applied functions according to the bygone and static imaginations of the African cultural past. Similarly Visitors' Interpretative Rock Art Centre in Twyfelfontein (Fig.8) by Nina Maritz Architect and DenisMcDonald Architect and Fish River Canyon Visitors' Centre by Nina Maritz Architect although being perceived as interesting and well blended into the landscape according to international trends, they remain vibrant as long as tourists are staying there.

Figure 7: Mowani Mountain Camp, Klaus Brandt Associated Architects, Namibia (Sachse, 2013).

Figure 8: Visitors' Interpretative Rock Art Centre (left), Nina Maritz Architect and Denis McDonald Architect, Twyfelfontein (right), Namibia (Sachse, 2013; McDonald, 2005).

Through the Other's Lens: Conclusions.

A European who visits the countries of South Africa and lives in a town having a modern architecture origin, and who knows African cultures and events from the apartheid period only from the sources written by European researchers, intuitively senses/perceives both the multidimensional African reality as well as the Ubuntu philosophy. Nonetheless both elements (multidimensional African reality and the Ubuntu philosophy) are difficult to conceptualize intellectually and precisely/accurately in adequate vocabulary terms by Europeans. For that European languages have no appropriate syntactic and semantic structures, which means that Europeans – even if familiar with scientific discourse - are not cognitively/mentally prepared for understanding African reality and philosophy. One of the reason for that is that scientific Western metalanguages, abstract terms and concepts have been deprived of a direct reference to the material content, still saved in African indigenous languages, and because of that are also not able to describe and explain the multidimensional reality and interconnectivity of all beings in it (Holland and Quinn, 1987). Thus, to the European abovementioned African multidimensionality results in the perceiving in any traditional behavior of African citizens (traditionally representing the respect to every

existence) romanticizing, uplifting and emotional affection towards nature (thus, according to the western dualist doctrine which juxtaposes the world of nature to the world of culture and civilization) and vernacularism. Mowani Mountain Camp (Fig.8) built for tourists inspired by Berg Damara's village (Malan, 1995), constitutes an example of architectural realization that comprises this approach. Those facts are the arguments suggesting why European ideological as well as abstract discourses should be disqualified as the theoretical grounds for the original African philosophy of designing architecture. Instead of it, the Ubuntu philosophy concerned in sustaining and maintaining multidimensional reality alive, prevents from the preference for the only one chosen perspective or ideology. It prevents also the architecture from the lack of the possibility for the universalization of such perspective and perception of it as the only possible and correct. That, in turn, allows for the Ubuntu discourse becoming the grounds for the reconciliation between black, white and coloured members of the societies.

African cultures seem to belong to those which have lived and prospered believing that an inherent harmony or beneficence in nature would provide for their needs through a technological sense, defined as a skill dependent on cultural and environmental circumstances (Ingold, 2000), working in the African context like the medium letting for maintaining the relations between spaces, times, objects and beings of multi-dimensional world. Western development of the communication technologies changed the understanding of the notion „the medium“ which – when accommodated by African citizens - consequently erases the technological sense. It has become one of the reasons for withdrawal of the members of the societies from the cultural heritage. The erased technological sense connecting people with multidimensional reality has been replaced by engineering. From the analytical point of view the main goal of the engineering technology is to produce the artefact serving as the base for the services. From this perspective the architectural design can be understood as the structured series of the translations of properties of the tools/services (as to the physical parameters, components) into/onto the functional demands. The engineering allows for the modification of the tool properties through the constant modification of the (instrumentalized) parameters of almost all kinds. This attributes to the engineering a modernization dynamism, universality and pervasiveness, treated by Western science as irreversible and inevitable (Ellul, 1964; Winner, 1978). Nonetheless among African cultures they become the main sources of the lack of respect for traditional heritage and ethics. In the face of the fact that the of western concepts of the development disregards traditional culture and identity, it is necessary to undertake the interdisciplinary (architectural, philosophical, cosmological, anthropological analysis even going back to the archeology of the African towns) with the participation of indigenous inhabitants, for re-discovering African roots of the architecture for the further design considering again a technological sense via the concept of the African systems of perception.

The engineering development constantly outpaces the capacity of individuals and social systems to adapt it. The increasing speed of introducing innovations makes it difficult to carry out the informal structures, planning, the design, and the functional coordination (even on the European continent). To decide whether the Western concepts of the development based on engineering, like this of the smart city, can be implemented into the African cities, it is necessary to recognize whether the technologies, especially those based on the new

digital medias, can play positive role in the maintaining cultural binds between different groups of the members of the society, on which further city development depends. Too fast assimilation of new technologies, in comparison to the low speed of the changes in the area of education, mentality and development of the cultural awareness and identity, does not fit to creative adaptation of them to the social development, threatening further erasing the natives from the indigenous cultures. Instead of the high technologies, the acceptance of the Ubuntu epistemology as the basis for shaping the architecture of the city allows for respecting the informal structures, acting as the first step towards the redefinition of the modern planning tools as the town planning tool. The open-ended town planning seems to be more appropriate as it allows for maintaining life-sustaining relations between people and the development/adaptation of the necessary technologies within the real needs, without destroying the technological sense, the lack of which deprived Africans of the contact with multidimensional nature after migration from the country to towns. Thus, the Ubuntu-based design should allow also for the reconciliation between the men, nature and the spaces through so called passive technologies. That can help the citizens in further approaching and implementing activities in terms of knowledge creation and development of the high engineering infrastructure, suitable for the natural environment and Ubuntu heritage. Finally, the Ubuntu-based philosophy of design would act as a medium letting for development of the technologies which would connect the designing of various scales (from buildings to towns), cultural resources and the new technologies with existing urban and architectural tissues in one reconciled wholeness.

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PHOTOS

Figure 1: Primary School, Gando, Burkina Faso (*Kéré*, 2004).

Figure 2: Alexandra Interpretation Centre, Johannesburg, South Africa (Hall, 2011).

Figure 3: Guga S'Thebe Arts & Culture Centre, Cape Town, South Africa (Phaidon Ed., 2004).

Figure 4a: Sachse, J., Single Quarters Market, Marais, Pretorious & Wenhold Architects, Windhoek, Namibia. 2013. Author: J. Sachse.

Figure 4b: Single Quarters Market, Marais, Pretorious & Wenhold Architects, Windhoek, Namibia, 2013. Author: A. Rynkowska- Sachse.

Figure 5: The Village, Barnard Mutua Architects, Windhoek, Namibia, 2013. Author: A. Rynkowska-Sachse.

Figure 6: Ernst & Young Headoffice, Wasserfall Muntig Architects, Windhoek, Namibia, 2013. Author: J. Sachse.

Figure 7: Mowani Mountain Camp, Klaus Brandt Associated Architects, Namibia, 2013
Author: J. Sachse.

Figure 8a: Visitors' Interpretation Rock Art Centre by Nina Maritz Architect and Denis McDonald Architect, Twyfelfontein, Namibia, 2013. Author: J. Sachse.

Figure 8b: The model of Visitors' Interpretation Rock Art Centre by Nina Maritz Architect and Denis McDonald Architect, Twyfelfontein, Namibia, 2005. Author: D. McDonald.